

**METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING AUDITORY ABILITY OF
STUDENTS IN ENGLISH WITH THE HELP OF INNOVATIVE
EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES**

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Annotation: The implementation of fundamental changes in English language teaching in our country shows the presence of various aspects and social conditions.

Key words: psycho-pedagogical conditions, theory and practice, traditional and interactive methods.

Introduction:

Readiness to implement foreign experience and methodical innovation in language teaching at all levels of the existing education system in our country, especially from educational managers to teachers, the presence of openness to it, the unique economic, spiritual and pedagogical potential of all regions of the country that it is sufficient, that the traditions of language teaching have been formed in these places and the readiness of pedagogical teams to redevelop it, that the material-economic and information-communication base for innovative teaching of foreign languages has been created;

-psychological-pedagogical conditions: full understanding and acceptance of the goals and tasks of the perspective strategy for teaching foreign languages by teachers and management at all stages of the educational system, theoretical and practical knowledge of the English language by teachers the presence of enthusiasm in the pedagogical team for regular work on themselves and improving their skills, the presence of a sense of satisfaction with their pedagogical activity,

the psychological and pedagogical readiness of the pedagogical team for the activity of forming a new, intellectually mature generation;

-educational and methodological conditions: written and published exercises based on the requirements of state documents, educational methodical manuals, electronic exercises, various tools, information communication devices, language cabinets and laboratories, classrooms and the availability of equipment, educational infrastructure at the level of demand, interdisciplinary integration within the framework of a foreign language, as well as a methodologically armed pedagogical team that is fully prepared for the innovative process; organizational-pedagogical conditions: the presence of the pedagogical team, in particular, its leadership, to regularly make innovative changes to the pedagogical process, pedagogical qualification improvement, the adoption of innovative ideas by the leader of the pedagogical team and opening the way for them to provide, the existence of efforts to provide the required equipment and etc.

Therefore, if we compare the current situation with the required level of teaching foreign languages on the basis of innovative pedagogical technologies, it is clear that some specific situations are in effect. Naturally, foreign languages, especially English, are required to make such fundamental changes puts the need to make changes in all areas of education on the agenda.

Conclusion:

During the research, the issue of using different methods in developing students' auditory ability was also studied. In this they:

- traditional method
- interactive methods
- use of language classrooms
- developed methods based on information-communication Computerized methods
- programmed methods
- the authorship methods of advanced pedagogues have been shown to use personal authorship methods developed and introduced by teachers of foreign languages

working at OTM. The results of the analysis show that 67 percent of pedagogues still use traditional methods in their work.